
Holistic Befriending of the Other in Buddhism

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Abstract: Buddhist befriending is holistic: it befriends human beings, even enemies, and nature too. In Buddhism one befriends others, in all circumstances and without discrimination, whether they are friends or enemies, offenders and prisoners, the poor and the needy. It also includes other religions and cultures as well as nature. We find several examples in the Buddhist texts, in history and in the contemporary world. This befriending is done with an altruistic spirit, with forbearance, loving friendship and compassion. As in all religions, however, there are exceptions in the texts, in history and in the modern world. Still, overall, Buddhism has been more peace-loving and non-violent than several other religions. Buddhist and Christian befriending do resemble each other, e.g., both are opposed to malice and both go to the extent of loving one's enemy. Although there are similarities, there are also differences between Buddhism and Christianity with regard to the presuppositions, the cultivation, motivation and expression of befriending. While

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divergent world-views result in such differences, Buddhists, Christians and others need to hearken to the call of peace and altruistic love, to heal a broken world and build bridges of friendship and harmony with other human beings and with nature.

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There are two forms of Buddhism, Hinayana and Mahayana. In Hinayana only one school is living, viz., Theravada, whose original texts are in the Pali language. In Mahayana there are many schools existing, and their original texts in India were in Sanskrit. Buddhist befriending is holistic: it befriends human beings, even enemies, and befriends nature too.

1. Befriending in the Buddhist Texts

A. Befriending Other Human Beings

a. Befriending Others in All Circumstances

In the Theravada scripture, the Buddha exhorts the disputatious monks of Kosambiya to live in mutual respect and harmony both in public and in private, asking them to be friendly in thought, word and deed, being united with one another in virtues as well as in their views. A Theravada text declares that whoever bears enmity even to thieves who sever one's limbs, with a saw, does not carry out the teaching of the Buddha. Even in such a circumstance, one should not be harsh to the thieves or hate them, but rather one should be kind and compassionate and cultivate friendliness (*metta*) towards them as well as towards the whole world. Mahayana texts exhort that one must forgive all types of offences (injury, insult, abuse, criticism), everywhere (in private and in public), at all times (past, present and future), in all circumstances (in sickness or health), in thought (not entertaining angry thoughts), word (not speaking harshly) and deed (not harming physically), without any exception (whether

friend, enemy or indifferent person), and however wicked the offending person or however terrible the injury may be.

In one of his previous lives as a Bodhisatta (in Sanskrit Bodhisattva), Gotama (a Pali form corresponding to the Sanskrit Gautama) Buddha was born as Kundalakumara, who was later known as Khantivadi [Sanskrit Ksantivadin], i.e., “One who preached the doctrine of forbearance”. Angry with Khantivadi, King Kalabu tested his forbearance, inflicting one agonizing torture after another. He first had him scourged all over his body, then had his hands and feet chopped off, and then his nose and ears cut off. Even though the king taunted him after every torment, Khantivadi never got angry, declaring himself to be a preacher and practitioner of forbearance. Finally, the king kicked him on his chest near the heart and walked off in a huff. The commander-in-chief requested Khantivadi to vent his wrath only on the king, but to spare the others and the kingdom. However, instead of taking revenge, Khantivadi uttered a blessing, “Long live the king!”

We notice in such instances that the ideal is not even to feel anger or hatred even in the most trying circumstances. We could say that, strictly speaking, there is nothing to forgive, for there is no offence taken in the first place. The ideal seems to be a sort of stoic attitude of not being perturbed at all.

b. Befriending Others without Discrimination

I have elsewhere shown how the Buddha endeavoured to reinterpret the caste system in terms of virtue and wisdom. Biologically, the human race is a single species: there is no distinction between the castes.

The *Brahmanavagga* of the *Dhammapada* defines a Brahmin as one who has banished sin (*bahitapapo ti brahmano*). The same *vagga* explains further that a person does not become a Brahmin through his family or birth, but by his virtuous life and deep knowledge. In the same vein, the *Vasalasutta* states that it is the wicked, ignorant and violent person who is an outcaste

(*vasala*). It is not by birth (*jacca*) but by deeds (*kammuna*) that one becomes a Brahmin or an outcaste. Thus the Buddha redefines caste in terms of ethical categories.

The Buddha's monastic Order (*sangha*) was open to all castes. There was no discrimination based on birth, occupation, social status or ritual purity. Women, however, were admitted by him only later – and that too, very reluctantly.

It may be remarked that the princely Buddha shows a preference for the Ksatriyas, for he maintains that they are superior to Brahmins, if one were to take lineage into consideration. He points out that a Ksatriya who has fallen into the deepest degradation is superior to a Brahmin who commits similar offences. When the four castes are listed, the Ksatriyas are frequently mentioned before the Brahmins. Is this a prejudice on the part of the Buddha, who was originally from the Ksatriya class, or of his disciples? Ultimately of course he does not put his trust in lineage. In the same *Ambatthasutta* where he makes the Ksatriya superior to the Brahmin, he makes it clear that it is the one who is perfect in wisdom and righteousness that is the best among deities and human beings. In this context, it is unfortunate that the three *Nikayas* among the monks in Sri Lanka are mostly based on caste differences.

By stressing the equality of all castes and reinterpreting the caste system in ethical terms, the Buddha brought new hope and the experience of human dignity to the many Buddhist converts from the scheduled castes who, in their quest for psychological liberation from the shackles of casteism, have followed Dr. Ambedkar into the Buddhist fold.

We may mention in passing that, although there is no discrimination with respect to caste, sexist and other prejudices do survive in the Buddhist Scriptures in keeping with their times. Monks and nuns are superior to the laity, particularly in Theravada. Women are inferior to men; in the Order nuns are subordinate to the monks: e.g., a nun even of a hundred years standing must first salute a monk even if he is just ordained;

she should never rebuke or abuse a monk; monks can admonish nuns, but not vice versa. Still, it is worthy of note that the rights of the wife and of the employee (including wages, bonuses and leave) are emphasized.

c. Befriending Enemies

In the Buddhist texts, one finds many reasons to motivate oneself to avoid resentment towards enemies. Buddhaghosa, a Theravada Buddhist, includes the following reasons in his *Visuddhimagga*: remembering the scriptural passages that exhort one to practise forbearance and avoid hatred, reflecting on the harmful effects of anger on oneself, developing compassion for one's enemies who will suffer in purgatories due to their succumbing to anger, recalling to mind the many examples of the Buddha, who in previous lives as a human adult or child and even as an animal did not entertain the slightest hatred towards his tormentors, reflecting that one's enemy may have been one's loving parents or brothers or sisters or sons or daughters in previous lives, realizing that the one with whom one is angry is not a substantial soul, but merely a series of momentary aggregates of various elements, and therefore one cannot make that person the target of one's anger.

Similarly, Mahayana texts, too, try to motivate one to practise forgiveness. Firstly, one should follow the teaching and example of the Buddhas in forgiveness. The Buddhas will not forgive people unless they forgive others who offend them. Secondly, in reference to the person to be forgiven one may reflect in this manner: the present enemy may have been one's friend, relative, or teacher in a former birth. Since Mahayana Buddhism does not believe in a finite soul, strictly speaking, there is no perpetrator of injuries and insults, nor is any one injured or insulted. All beings are evanescent and subject to pain and suffering, and so one should rather lighten their burden than be angry and unforgiving. The adversaries are conditioned by the results of their deeds (*karman*) in past lives, and are therefore not acting freely. Thirdly, one may also think with regard to oneself in the following vein: one is

suffering insult and injury as a consequence of one's own evil deeds in previous existences; one's enemies are actually one's friends and beneficiaries for they preserve one from such worldly goods as wealth and fame, and give one the golden opportunity to practise forbearance, which leads to salvation. Fourthly, one should ponder over the ill effects of an angry and unforgiving attitude: it results in terrible punishments in various purgatories, and wipes out the merit one has gained through several lives. Hence, it is better to bear up with the comparatively negligible sufferings inflicted on one in this life than face terrible tortures in the future. Revenge always brings evil consequences on oneself. Being at peace with others results in great happiness to oneself. Often one is unforgiving because of pride, which needs to be replaced by the spirit of humble service. Finally, mercy and love urge us to forgive others.

On occasion, the Buddha himself brings about reconciliation. In the Introduction to the *Kunalajataka*, it is reported that when the Koliya and Sakyan tribes were about to engage in a bloody battle over the right to the waters of the river Rohini, the Buddha persuaded them to desist from fighting by making them realize that there was no point in killing warriors of priceless value for the sake of some water that had comparatively little worth. Not all, however, paid heed to the Buddha's mediations. He was unable to persuade the stubborn monk Tissa to ask forgiveness for not welcoming some visiting monks with respect and hospitality. Tissa was unforgiving because he was angry with those monks for having abused him for this fault of omission. In fact, in a previous life too he was not willing to ask pardon.

d. Befriending Offenders and Prisoners

Unlike several Hindu texts that, in addition to expiation and reformatory punishment, also prescribe retributive and deterrent punishment, Theravada texts recommend punishment only after all other means of settling a dispute have been tried out, such as discussion, appeal to reason, repentance, etc., and even then, the punishment to be meted out is more on the milder and lighter side.

Theravada texts do not advocate capital punishment. So also, Mahayana texts are against capital punishment and amputation, and caution that, when punishment is to be administered, it should be with compassion. Justice must be restorative, not retributive. It should also be clarified that, although justice in the near future is not always insisted upon, eventual justice will normally take place, for it is based on the law of *karman*; however, as in devotional Hinduism, divine beings in devotional Mahayana can forgive sins as well as wipe out, at least partially, the punishment due to sins.

e. Befriending Those in Need

Prompted by compassion, the Bodhisattvas give generously not only to relatives, friends and dependents, but also to all those who ask for help, to the poor, the pitiable, the beggars. They give away not only external things like their house, spouses, children, etc., but they also part with their hands, feet, head, limbs, etc.; indeed, they sacrifice everything. They even transfer their own merit to others for their welfare and wellbeing, both physical and spiritual, and even take upon themselves the sufferings of others. They do all this and more at the appropriate time, with respect and the intention of promoting the welfare of all; besides they do not expect anything in return.

Both Theravada and Mahayana texts narrate hundreds of stories portraying the selfless and absolutely generous gifts of property, limb and life by men and women and even animals. Several texts, both in Theravada and in Mahayana, tell the story of the hare who, having no food, offers a guest his own flesh. Similarly, both traditions narrate the story of King Sivi (Sanskrit Sibi) who became blind by donating his eyes. The most famous story, again in both traditions, in this context of selfless and generous giving, is that of Vessantara (Sanskrit Visvantara) who, even after being banished by the king for his excessive generosity, gives away his horses and chariot, and even his children and wife. A Sanskrit Hinayana text narrates the touching story of an

extremely poor woman who gives away even the one piece of cloth that she was wearing.

Mahayana texts emphasize compassion (*karuna*) towards others. I mention a couple of examples. After Vimalakirti accepted from Sudatta the pearl necklace, whose value was a hundred thousand (gold pieces), Vimalakirti divided it into two halves and gave one half to the poor of the town who were disdained by those who were present at the sacrifice offered by Sudatta earlier, and gave the other half to the Tathagata Dusprasaha. Vimalakirti also declared that the donor who, without making any distinctions, impartially, and without expecting any recompense, donates gifts to the poor of the town, who are as worthy of the gifts as the Tathagata, performs the sacrifice completely. Santideva exclaims, “May I relieve the sorrow of all beings, may I be the doctor and attendant of all who are ill, until disease does not arise. With rains of food and drink, may I destroy the agony of hunger and thirst. In the famine of the intermediary ages, may I be drink and food. May I be an imperishable storehouse for poor beings, and may I attend upon them with diverse means of subsistence. I sacrifice, without expectation, my own being, pleasures and auspicious things to accomplish the goal of all beings. Abandoning everything is Nirvana; if all has to be given up by me, it is best that it be given to beings. May I be a protector of the unprotected, the caravan leader for those on a journey, a boat, a bridge, a conduit for those who desire the further Shore. I would be a lamp for those seeking a lamp, a bed for those wishing to have a bed, a slave to those wanting a slave.”

In this context of compassion, we must particularly mention the most popular Bodhisattva Avalokitesvara or Padmapani, who is the very embodiment of compassion, and even goes to the worst purgatory and takes on the sufferings of the tormented beings there. Possibly, because of his great compassion, he became feminine in countries like China and Japan.

f. Befriending People of Other Religions

The Buddha declares that he did not preach the Buddhist religion (Sanskrit *Dharma*) in separate portions: one pertaining to the Disciples' Vehicle, another to the Vehicle of the Pratyekabuddhas and a third for the Mahayana. Whoever makes such distinctions is confused and rejects the true *Dharma* by describing it as divided. Here no distinction is made between various Buddhist traditions.

In reference to other religions, the Buddha assures Nigrodha that, in wanting to teach the Buddhist religion (Pali *Dhamma*), he does not wish to get disciples for himself by alienating people of other religions from their teachers, rules, ways of life and right doctrines or by confirming them in their wrong views; all he intends is to help them get rid of things that cause corruption, suffering and rebirth. At another time, the Buddha tells Dhammika that the one who reviles sages of other traditions who are self-composed and free from passion obtains great demerit (*apunna*). It should be noted, however, that in the very next verse he adds that the one who reviles the Buddha's disciple who is accomplished in views (*ditthi-sampanna*), attains even greater demerit.

B. Befriending Nature

Gotama Buddha died of blood dysentery after eating a dish called *sukara-maddava* (soft pork). Scholars have different opinions as to whether this *sukara* was pork or a vegetarian dish made from such items as a sprout or a mushroom, etc. However, the earliest Pali commentaries identify it as pork. In the *Amagandhasutta* it is pointed out that destruction of life, cutting, binding, injustice, harshness, anger, envy, slander, injury, cruelty, disrespect, greed, hostility, etc. have the foul odour of rotting meat, but not so the eating of meat. When Buddhist monks went on their begging rounds, they were expected to accept whatever was put into their begging bowls. Early Buddhists were therefore not strict vegetarians. Nevertheless, in time Theravadins became increasingly vegetarian. A monk had to avoid eating animals

that were seen or heard by him, or suspected to have been deliberately killed for him. Theravada Buddhists should not be butchers, hunters and fisher folk, and should avoid any job that entails cruelty such as being an executioner or jailer. If they take up such occupations, they are tormentors of others. Buddhism also reacted against the sacrificial killing of animals.

Coming now to Mahayana, the eighth chapter of the *Saddharmalankavatasutra* is wholly dedicated to making people turn away from meat-eating. Although a good part of the chapter is in reference to Bodhisattvas, it is clearly meant for all the Buddha's disciples (*sisya*). In contrast to the earlier exceptions made by Theravada texts, this *sutra* categorically states that it is not true that meat is permissible when it is not killed or caused to be killed by oneself and not deliberately prepared for oneself by another. It further asserts that, even though exceptions have been made here and there in canonical texts (*desanapatha*, lit. directive or instructional texts), in this *sutra* flesh is unconditionally forbidden for all, in whatever form, manner or place. In most of the chapter it puts forward many reasons for avoiding non-vegetarian food. For example, given the fact that transmigration has been going on for a very long time, there cannot be any animal or bird who at one time or another has not been one's own mother or father or some other relative. How then can one bring oneself to eat a living being that is of the same nature as oneself? Flesh, which is born of semen, blood, etc., pollutes one's purity; it brings demerit, leads to rebirth as a carnivorous animal and in various demonic forms; it prevents knowledge, and is an obstacle to salvation (*moksa*). Out of compassion we should refrain from consuming meat, for when an animal sees a meat-eater it is frightened for its life. Flesh has a foul smell even when burned, and spoils one's good name among noble (*arya*) people, whose food is vegetarian; meat-eating invites censure against Buddhism. Looking upon all beings as our very own (child), we should refrain from devouring their flesh. Non-vegetarians suffer from disturbed sleep, terrible dreams and ill health. The consumption of meat successively

results in pride, erroneous imagination, passion, delusion of the mind, and lack of liberation.

Buddhist texts are also against the unnecessary destruction of vegetative life. A monk should abstain from destroying the growth of seeds and vegetables. The destruction of plant-life by monks is a *pacittiya* (“expiation”) type of offence, which requires confession. Monks were of course permitted to eat vegetables, to use twigs to brush their teeth or to use herbal medicines. The basic idea is to avoid unnecessary violence even to plant life and to develop sensitivity to the whole of nature. In fact, it is a *pacittiya* fault even to dig the earth or cause it to be dug: this is in order to avoid doing violence to the living organisms and seeds in the earth.

2. Befriending in Buddhist History

A. Asoka and Honen Befriending Enemies

In the 13th Rock Edict, the Emperor Asoka publicly expresses his remorse and confesses how the carnage at Kalinga caused him great anguish. He also declares that he pardons, as far as it is possible, all those who have wronged him. He makes peace with the people living in the forests. He wishes all beings to be free from injury and to enjoy gentleness or joyousness. He even took care to omit the 13th Edict from the texts carved on the rocks in Kalinga, lest even his words of repentance would serve as a spark to re-ignite adverse emotions in the Kalingas by reviving the memory of his fateful attack on their country.

The father of Honen, the leader of the Japanese Jodo-shu school, was fatally wounded by a gang of robbers who attacked their home. On his deathbed, his father exhorted his son never to take revenge but rather to pray for the salvation of his father as well as of the attackers.

B. Befriending Other Cultures

Already in India Buddhism assumed different forms, even though one kind may have been considered heretical by another. More importantly, when Buddhism spread to other countries in Asia, it took pains to inculturate itself into the different cultures it encountered, evolving into a wide variety of forms with differing beliefs and practices.

Perhaps there is no other world religion that has inculturated itself so much as Buddhism. Already from early times, Mahayana made efforts at translating its Scriptures into different languages. Sri Lankan Buddhists developed the practice of chanting the *Pirith* (chanting of *suttas* for the sake of protection), and participating in the Kandy Perahera, in which statues of Hindu deities of four temples are carried in procession along with the reliquary of the Buddha's tooth. In Burma and Thailand, Buddhists venerate spirits called Nats and Phis respectively, and in both countries, it is the custom for every male to spend some time living the life of a monk. Chinese Buddhism integrated Taoist mythology, and emphasized nature mysticism and faith. Techniques of *wen-ta* (question and answer) and *kung-an* ("riddles") were developed to help achieve liberation (*tun-wu*). In Japan the Tendai school, which synthesized Mahayana and Theravada, reinterpreted ordination as a sacrament. The Jodo schools of Honen and Shinran emphasized faith much more than the corresponding Chinese Ching-t'u school. Zen integrated secular arts like archery and sword-fencing. It went further than China in developing still more the use of "riddles" (*koan*) and in cultivating a greater closeness to nature, manifested, for instance, in bamboo and rock gardens. Although initially Buddhism criticized the religions of Tibet as primitive and barbarous, it soon developed a uniquely Tibetan genre. It adopted the use of prayer-wheels, prayer-flags and prayer-walls, as well as trances and masked dances. Faith in the lama (*blama*) or *guru* was of the utmost importance. Also characteristic of Tibetan Buddhism is the belief in incarnation lamas. For example, the Dalai Lama is the indirect

descent of the *Bodhisattva* Avalokitesvara and the Panchen Lama is the indirect descent of the Buddha Amitabha.

Thus Buddhism did not confine itself to one culture. Its openness, universal outlook and respect for pluralism enabled it to inculturate itself deeply in different cultures. It should be noted that in spite of the two main divisions of Buddhism acculturating themselves to different cultures, each still preserves a certain basic unity. The various Mahayana schools, which have incarnated themselves much more than Theravada, display a wide divergence in practices, rituals, meditational techniques, etc.; however, they differ but little in their philosophical or theological understanding of reality. In this way, each branch of Buddhism is able to maintain a unique unity in diversity.

C. Befriending Nature

In his 5th Pillar Edict King Asoka exempted several animals from slaughter, e.g., parrots, geese, swans, bats, boneless fish, etc., and certain animals when they were pregnant. He also prohibited the killing of fish and certain animals on particular auspicious days. In his 1st Rock Edict he forbade the sacrifice of all animals in his palace. Formerly very many living beings were killed daily for his table; but he decreed that only three would be slain: two peacocks and one deer, and the latter would not be killed invariably. In fact, he said, even these would not be slaughtered in the future.

In Theravada there developed the practice of setting up sanctuaries for birds and animals as well as tanks for fish, where they could move about freely without being hunted or caught. This was called *abhaya-dana* (the gift of fearlessness).

Similar to the case of Theravada, the custom, and even ceremony, of freeing living creatures arose in Mahayana too. It consisted in purchasing birds, animals and fish that had been captured, and setting them free in their own habitats. In China and Japan, too, different kings prohibited the eating of meat and advocated non-violence towards animals, birds and fish. It should

be noted, however, that some Mahayana schools are non-vegetarian, while Theravada is vegetarian.

3. Contemporary Examples of Befriending

A. *Befriending Other Human Beings*

I shall first give some instances of modern Theravada Buddhists and then move on to present-day Mahayana Buddhists.

a. *Ariyaratne of Sri Lanka*

Dr. Ahangamage Tudor Ariyaratne of Sri Lanka started his Sarvodaya (Uplift or Awakening of All) Sramadana (Donation of Labour) Movement in Sri Lanka between 1956 and 1958, and nurtured it for many years. Basing himself on traditional Theravada principles and also reinterpreting some of them to give them a social thrust, he set up volunteer work camps for social upliftment. Ariyaratne's Sarvodaya catered to ten fundamental needs of society: a pure and attractive environment, sufficient supply of pure water, basic requirements of clothing, an adequate diet, simple residential facilities, basic health services, communication infrastructure, fuel and other energy needs, a comprehensive education for daily living, and cultural and spiritual development. In every village Sarvodaya tried to set up six groups: pre-school toddlers, schoolchildren, mothers, youth, farmers, and the elderly. Each of these groups is conscientized and helped to participate, in varying degrees, in a holistic and all-round development of the village.

Although Ariyaratne is Sinhalese, he extended his hand of friendship and collaboration to the Tamil Hindus in Sri Lanka. His Sarvodaya played an important role as peace builder in the severe ethnic conflicts of Sri Lanka. It analysed the causes of the conflicts, worked out comprehensive programmes to resolve the problems in a humane manner, encouraged Sinhalese and Tamilians to work together as volunteers in each other's villages, organized peace meditations, peace camps, peace pilgrimages and

marches, and peace meetings and conferences; initiated ways and means for the return and rehabilitation of refugees; and, for both the militants and the armed forces, to lay down their arms and return to civilian life, through techniques of inner transformation. Although Sarvodaya was a Buddhist movement, it was open to others: Tamilians (many of whom were Hindus) too played important leadership roles in Sarvodaya peace initiatives. Tamilians who collaborated with Sarvodaya looked upon it not so much as a Sinhalese Buddhist organization, but a Sri Lankan association. In 1994 Ariyaratne met leaders of the LTTE, in an attempt to bring about reconciliation and peace.

b. Uttarananda of Sri Lanka

The Sri Lankan monk H. Uttarananda, who was a member of the now defunct Humanist Bhikkhus' Association (*Manava-hitavadi Bhikkhu Sangamaya*), proposed a Buddhist-Humanist view of the national ethnic problem in Sri Lanka. Following the typical Buddhist "middle path", he wanted to avoid the two extremes of a Sinhala Buddhist State and a free Eelam State. He acknowledged the inhuman atrocities perpetrated on Tamils in 1983 and thereafter by racist fanatics and governments, and was able to sympathetically understand the exasperated violent reactions of Tamils whose pent up rage boiled over due to the prolonged racist attitudes of successive governments. He called for reconciliation and strengthening of racial unity and peace.

c. The Four Mahanayakes or Patriarchs of Sri Lanka

In a Press Conference in Tokyo on 3rd June 2002, the four Mahanayakes or "Patriarchs" of the Theravada Buddhist Order of Sri Lanka publicly released a Press Statement, which declared that the Order was for peace and development in Sri Lanka and solicited the support of the Japanese people in the peace process and in confidence-building measures which would benefit all three communities affected by the war, viz., the Sinhalese, the Tamils and the Muslims. The Sri Lankan newspaper *The Island* reported that the Mahanayake of Asgiriya conferred his blessings

on both the UNP Government of Ranil Wickremasinghe as well as the LTTE in their efforts to restore peace through peace talks held in Thailand.

d. Sulak Sivaraksa of Thailand

Sulak Sivaraksa of Thailand is, on the one hand, rooted in the Buddhist Scripture. On the other hand, he frequently reinterprets traditional texts and doctrines to give them an explicit social and developmental orientation.

Sivaraksa founded a number of social welfare organizations or voluntary Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs), in which people work with dedication for the uplift of the poor, both in the villages and the cities. Inspired by spiritual principles, they reach out to those in need – exploited men, women and children – and help them, through non-violent means, to regain their human dignity and stand on their own feet. They also pay attention to ecology and the environment: they work for integral and sustainable development.

What is particularly notable is that Sivaraksa also engages in interreligious dialogue and cooperative interreligious social action for development. He started the Thai Interreligious Commission for Development. He also participated in the World Conference on Religion and Peace in Melbourne. He collaborated with a number of Catholic and Protestant development organizations in different parts of the world. He mentions several dialogue meetings with Christians, where all were equal, challenging one another in friendship, and working together for social uplift. Over many years, he was able to build bonds of friendship with individual Buddhists of other traditions, as well as with Christians, Jews, Muslims and Hindus in different parts of the world.

e. The Late Maha Ghosananda of Thailand

In war-torn Cambodia, the late Maha Ghosananda of Thailand, five-time Nobel Peace Prize nominee, led nine *Dhammayietras* [Khmer or Cambodian for the Sanskrit *Dharmayatras*] or Pil-

grimaces of Truth to promote peace between rival Cambodian groups. Often opponents met and walked together in the spirit of reconciliation. In his first *Dhammayietra*, he preached repeatedly, “The suffering of Cambodia has been deep. From this suffering comes Great Compassion. Great Compassion makes a peaceful heart. A peaceful heart makes a peaceful person. A peaceful person makes a peaceful family. A peaceful family makes a peaceful community. A peaceful community makes a peaceful nation. A peaceful nation makes a peaceful world”. When, returning from his monastery in Thailand, he paid his first visit to the Sakeo Cambodian refugee camp, he distributed copies of the *Metta-sutta*, a Buddhist Theravada scriptural text on loving kindness or friendship, and exhorted the refugees to forgive their persecutors. A leader of the Khmer Rouge requested Maha Ghosananda to visit Thailand and build a Buddhist temple on the border of Cambodia, and the latter readily agreed. Many were scandalized that he was helping an “enemy”. However, he pointed out that love did not discriminate between good or bad; in fact, it was those who were deviants who needed loving kindness all the more because, often enough, virtue vanished from them because they did not experience the warmth of empathy from others. Quoting Mahatma Gandhi, he said that reconciliation consisted in destroying enmity, not enemies; loving kindness removed ignorance from adversaries as well as from us: we all needed to be freed.

f. Aung San Suu Kyi of Myanmar

Nobel Laureate, Aung San Suu Kyi of Myanmar, was at a public rally at the Shwedagon Pagoda in 1998. She appealed to the people to let bygones be bygones, to manifest their innate ability to forgive, not to abandon their traditional love for the armed forces and to resort to peaceful means of walking hand in hand with the authorities to build a united Burma. When she was freed in 1995, after six years of house arrest by the military, and that, too, in spite of a landslide victory of her party, she expressed appreciation for the conciliatory tenor of the announcement of release by her captors, and highlighted the need for dialogue rather

than confrontation for the restoration of peace. She declared that she did not harbour any bitterness against anyone for the treatment she received during those six long years.

g. The Dalai Lama of Tibet

Let me now turn to Mahayana examples. Relying on Mahayana principles, the Dalai Lama, who was awarded the Nobel Peace Prize, has been advocating social responsibility and concern for nature. He has always embraced the policy of peaceful resistance to the Chinese, who occupied Tibet in 1950. He refers to the Chinese as his brothers and sisters and is motivated by tolerance, compassion and love. While wanting autonomy, he admits the fact that Tibet would continue to be linked with China. In his Nobel Peace Prize Lecture, in speaking of the atrocities committed by the Chinese against Tibetans and their country and culture, he said that he did not speak with a heart filled with hatred or anger against the Chinese for, he added, they too were human beings striving for happiness and were entitled to compassion.

Elsewhere he also points out that enemies are valuable because they help us to advance in spiritual qualities such as forbearance and mental fortitude. He admits that, had he stayed in Lhasa, he might have been isolated and conservative. Hence, he is indebted to the Chinese since his exile helped broaden his perspectives. He felt very sad that Tibetans were infuriated against the Chinese and took part in burning Chinese vehicles. His purpose in narrating the trials and tribulations of the Tibetan people was not out of vindictiveness or hostility towards the Chinese, but in order to inform the public. He also felt that many well-meaning Chinese were simply not aware of what was going on in Tibet.

The Dalai Lama admits, however, that when people exploit the sincerity of a person, it may be necessary to retort. However, although on the surface level an apt reaction is resorted to, there should be an underlying spirit of forbearance, compassion and tolerance, without bearing any ill feelings. Our real enemies are not outside us but inside us, e.g., arrogance, wrath and envy,

and we have to wage a war against these internal foes. World peace cannot be achieved without realizing that we are all sisters and brothers, and without cultivating kindness and compassion. However, this is not possible without inner transformation.

h. Thich Nhat Hahn of Vietnam

The Vietnamese monk Thich Nhat Hanh did not bear any hatred towards the Catholic Diem regime that persecuted him, nor to the Viet Cong or the U.S. soldiers who attacked Vietnam. He could find excuses for the atrocities perpetrated by U.S. soldiers in Vietnam, attributing these to their hard life in the swamps and jungles infested by mosquitoes and other insects, and to their being in constant danger of death. Although initially angry, he did not blame a sea-pirate who had raped a twelve-year old girl, thinking that if he had had the same historical, economic and educational background as that pirate he would probably have behaved in the same way. This attitude of Thich Nhat Hanh is based on the Buddhist doctrine of Dependent or Conditioned Co-production (*pratitya-samutpada*; Pali *patticca-saumuppada*), according to which no being or event arises without a conditioning factor: this (resulting) being or event is because that (preceding) being or event is; this (resulting) being or event is not because that (preceding) being or event is not. It thus helps the Buddhist to pay attention to attenuating circumstances, and hence be more understanding and forgiving.

B. Befriending Nature

A number of Theravada monks in Thailand are giving leadership in befriending nature. Phrakhru Manas Natheepitak, the abbot of Wat Bodharma, is said to be the first who came up with the novel idea of a ceremony that he called Tree Ordination, in which trees are wrapped in the saffron robes of Theravada monks. Many other monks follow this practice. When people see the saffron robes wrapped around the trees, they refrain from felling the trees. Similarly, another monk, Phrakhru Pitak Nanthakun, in addition to a more elaborate Tree Ordination ceremony, also

instituted a ritual for sanctifying the river Nan, an important river in Thailand. This ceremony is modelled on a traditional rite for lengthening the life span of human beings and domestic animals. He, and other monks after him, have conducted this ceremony on different occasions and have reserved certain parts of the river as safe havens for fish so that fish can multiply without human interference.

The Mahayana Buddhist country of Bhutan has a law that 60% of its land would be covered forever with forests. The King and Queen of Bhutan announced the birth of their first child on 5th February 2016. On 6th March 2016 the entire nation celebrated the prince's birth by planting 108000 saplings. In June 2015, a team of 100 volunteers planted 49672 saplings in one hour, setting a Guinness record.

4. Befriending the Others with Friendship and Compassion

Buddhists approach all forms of befriending, of humans as well as nature, in the spirit of friendship (Pali *metta*; Sanskrit *maitri*) and compassion (*karuna*). They are two of the four Buddhist virtues called *Brahma-viharas* (Sublime States or Abidings); the third *Brahma-vihara* is joy (*mudita*) and the fourth is equanimity (Pali *upekkha*; Sanskrit *upeksa*). While Theravada gives more importance to friendship, Mahayana emphasizes compassion more. All the four Sublime States are to be cultivated or developed through meditation.

In Theravada friendship essentially consists in the wish that all beings may be happy. Just as a mother would protect her only child at the risk of her own life, even so one should cultivate unlimited love towards all beings. In Mahayana friendship is a love that consists in the hope, prayer, keen desire for, and joy at, the happiness of others, without passion and the seeking of reward. It is of three kinds depending on whether it is directed towards living beings, phenomena (*dharma*) or no particular object. Hence, both in Theravada as well as in Mahayana, friendship is altruistic

love, and therefore *metta* or *maitri* is also translated as loving kindness.

Compassion includes all altruistic aspects of love. Bodhisattvas feel compassion for living beings like a father for his dear and only son. The wise love all beings more than themselves, or their spouses, children, friends and relatives. Tormented by the sufferings of others, the compassionate ones do not look for their own happiness. Bodhisattvas desire enlightenment first for all beings and not for themselves. In some passages, we notice that the Bodhisattvas act for the benefit of others (*para*) as well as themselves (*atman*). However, in some other passages, we find that the texts speak only of the good of others, and not love for oneself, thus emphasizing altruism much more.

5. Some Exceptions

As in all religions, in Buddhism too, there is doubtless a gap between the ideal and the existential. Here are a few instances:

A. In the Texts

In the Theravada Scripture, the Buddha asserts that no Ajivaka has ever brought suffering to an end [i.e., attained liberation]; nay, in the ninety-one aeons (*kappa*) that he remembers, he does not know of any Ajivaka who reached even the temporary heaven (*sagga*), except one – but he was a believer in *karman* [i.e., he was not an orthodox Ajivaka].

In a Mahayana scriptural text, it is said that those who scorn, and do not have faith in a *sutra* like the *Saddharmapundarikasutra* are destined to fall into Avici (the lowest level of purgatory), and to suffer many other torments, diseases, ill-treatment, etc. In fact, even a whole aeon (*kalpa*) is not enough to enumerate such a person's countless ills.

One of the chronicles of Sri Lanka, the *Mahavamsa*, often portrays the island's Tamilians as enemies of the Sinhalese. Even though he had conquered King Elara, King Dutthagamani was disconsolate for he realized that he had slaughtered millions in the battle. But some Arahants consoled him by telling him that

this action of his would not prevent him from attaining a temporary heaven. He had killed only one and a half human beings, i.e., those who had declared themselves to be Buddhists, fully or partially. The rest were unbelievers and immoral, not worth any more than mere animals. He would bring glory to Buddhism and so should not let his heart be troubled.

B. In History

In Sri Lanka, a Theravada king seized a Mahayana monastery and burnt its scriptural texts. In Burma King Anuruddha (Anawratha) of Punnagama (Pagan) attacked the kingdom of Sudhamapura (Thaton) in order to seize a copy of the Scriptures and the relics of the Buddha, which King Manohari (Manuha) had refused to send him when requested to do so.

The Mahayana Tibetan Dge-lugs-pa (Gelugpa) school – the Dalai Lama belongs to this group – often persecuted other Buddhist schools, attacking and destroying their monasteries and books. Tibetan Buddhists fought many wars against each other. In Japan the monk Nichiren (1222-1282), who founded the militant, nationalistic Mahayana school called Nichirenshu, launched a vituperative attack on all other Buddhist schools, denouncing them as heretics and holding them responsible for the many natural calamities and political troubles of Japan: “Nembutsu is hell; the Zen are devils; Shingon is national ruin; and the Risshu are traitors to the country.” From the sixteenth century right up to the beginning of the twentieth century, the Buddhists rabidly persecuted Shamanism in Mongolia: images and other sacred objects were destroyed and shamans were burnt alive or forced to renounce their faith. In the face of such facts, the assertion of Rahula Walpola, viz., that Buddhism had never persecuted or caused bloodshed in converting others and propagating its faith, will have to be modified.

C. In Modern Times

In the ethnic conflicts in Sri Lanka between the Sinhalese and Tamilians, there were nation-wide riots and massacres; temples

were destroyed and images were desecrated. It is reported that, even in the refugee camps for Tamilians, there are many atrocities against them. At present, Buddhist nationalist groups in Sri Lanka, of which the Bodu Bala Sena (Buddhist Power Army) or BBS and Sinhala Ravaya (Sinhalese Roar) are the most prominent, are leading a hate campaign against people of other religions and doing violence to them. In Myanmar monks played a part in the terrible Buddhist-Muslim riots of 1938. In the Great Recital of the Pali Canon in Burma (Myanmar) in 1954, monks who were not Theravadins were considered as lay people and given lower seats among the laity.

In more recent times the military junta in Myanmar displayed a violent attitude to Aung San Suu Kyi and perpetrated various atrocities on people, such as rape, torture and forced labour. At present, there is widespread persecution of Rohingya Muslims by Buddhists in Myanmar. In Cambodia, Pol Pot and the Khmer Rouge committed extensive genocide.

Let us now mention a couple of examples from Mahayana. The Japanese imperialism and its atrocities, especially in the initial years of their colonial rule in Korea, are well known. Koreans were coerced to work in Japanese factories or drafted as soldiers and sent to the front. Thousands of Korean women were recruited as “comfort women”, virtually as sexual slaves for Japanese soldiers. The Japanese attempted to force Korean Buddhism to merge with Japanese forms of Buddhism. They also advocated the practice of married monks. Later, within Korean Buddhism itself, there was a schism on the issue of married versus celibate monks. The conflict between these two rival groups of monks, which also included physical violence, has a long and chequered history in Korea. In spite of the Dalai Lama’s plea for non-violence, Tibetans, including monks, have been reacting violently against the Chinese regime.

Certainly, the peace-loving, gentle and broad-minded Buddha would not have approved of such fundamentalist, intolerant and belligerent actions on the part of his followers. Sincere Buddhists

will deplore the many forms of Buddhist intolerance. However, Buddhism has shown itself more peace-loving than several other religions. The historian Toynbee wrote, “The three Judaic religions have a record of intolerance, hatred, malice, uncharitableness and persecution that is black by comparison with Buddhism’s record.” Still, Buddhism must once again hearken to the call of the Buddha for friendship, to forget narrowmindedness, go beyond bigotry, and embrace the other in selfless altruism.

6. Comparison with Christian Befriending

Buddhist and Christian befriending do resemble each other, e.g., both are opposed to malice and both go to the extent of loving one’s enemy. However, there are many important differences, springing from their different world-views. Christians forgive others because otherwise God will not forgive them. But Theravada Buddhism does not admit any Supreme Being; hence the motivation is not the same. In Theravada, charity begins at home: one loves or practises friendliness first towards oneself; only then can one extend friendliness towards others.

In Christianity, the person befriended has intrinsic worth: the person is a child of God and has an immortal soul. In Theravada, on the other hand, the one who is befriended is neither created by a God nor has a soul: each individual is just a series of momentary aggregates, subject to the law of *kamma* [Sanskrit *karman*] (results of past deeds), and therefore does not have intrinsic worth, but should still be befriended. In Mahayana the human being has even less worth, for the individual does **not** exist even for one moment; only the Adi (First) Buddha, one of the technical terms for the Supreme and Only Being, exists. Yet, paradoxically, the ideal is to unilaterally befriend others who do not really exist even for a moment, except on the level of ignorance and from the practical point of view. In a sense, according to the doctrine of dependent co-production, dependence exists – which, in modern times, is further interpreted even as interdependence or a sort of interrelatedness – but individuals do not exist. Moreover, the interrelatedness in the Mahayana world-view is on the ontologi-

cal level; ultimately there is absolute identity. As a result, while in Christianity one concentrates on overcoming differences between alienated people, in Mahayana one transcends these differences. Hence in Mahayana one can more easily identify oneself even with the oppressor.

While the cultivation and expression of Christian friendship is, in some measure, spontaneous, personal, and generally emotional, Theravada befriending, even if it comes naturally in the case of those who have attained perfection in it, is developed through a systematic, calculated method and expressed in a more impersonal, detached and emotionally more sedate manner.

Christian befriending is based on the inter-personal, communitarian world-view. In Theravada on the other hand, one can only do good or harm to oneself, for each one is reaping the fruits of one's own past deeds (Pali *kamma* or Sanskrit *karman*). One can help another only indirectly by one's example, by trying not to provoke resentment and anger in others and by the tranquil, detached vibrations of friendship (*metta*) sent out in different directions. Disagreeing with an acrobat, his apprentice pointed out that they would perform their act successfully not by watching out for each other but by each one watching out for himself.

In Christianity, it is often said that God will not forgive us unless we forgive others. In Mahayana, too, the Buddhas will not forgive people unless they forgive others. However, it should be noted that even here there are differences. For example, it is not the Buddhas and Bodhisattvas who are the highest, but it is the Adi Buddha that is the Supreme Being. The dealings of the Mahayana Buddhists, however, are with the former.

The Buddhist doctrine of reincarnation motivates one to forgive and be reconciled, but Christianity does not believe in rebirth. On the other hand, for Christianity the person has intrinsic worth, but this is not the case with Buddhism. Hence the motivation for practising forgiveness and reconciliation is also different in the two traditions.

Unlike Christian befriending, Buddhist befriending is more universal, since it is extended also to nature and not just to human beings. However, possibly due to influence from Buddhism and other Eastern religions, and with a growing awareness of the environment in the West, modern Christianity is moving in the direction of befriending nature too and even making restitution by efforts to heal the earth and by recognizing the rights of animals and plants.

One of the practical differences between Christianity and Buddhism is that Buddhism prescribes meditational techniques to help one develop a befriending disposition: merely making a good resolution is not enough. Christianity, on the other hand, only exhorts people to befriend, forgive and be reconciled, but there are no methods or techniques that enable people to become more befriending and forgiving and more reconciled.

Thus, we see that, while there are similarities in befriending between Christianity and Buddhism, there are many distinctions arising from the divergent world-views not only of Christianity but also of Theravada and Mahayana. These differences are found not only with regard to the presuppositions, but also in reference to the motivation as well as the expression of befriending.

While granting that divergent world-views result in differences with regard to the nature, motivation and expression of befriending, Buddhists, Christians and others need to hearken to the call of peace and altruistic love, to heal a broken world and build bridges of friendship and harmony.

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Notes

1. Kosambiyasutta, in Majjhimanikaya, pt I, 48, p. 393ff. Unless otherwise stated, all references to the Buddhist Sanskrit texts cited by me are to the Darbhanga ed., published by the Mithila Institute, Bihar. However, references to the Dhammapada-atthakatha and the Jataka-atthakatha are from the Dhammagiri edition published by the Vipassana Research Institute, Igatpuri, Maharashtra.
2. Kakacupamasutta, in Majjhimanikaya, pt I, 21.5.20, pp. 172-173.
3. See the texts cited in Har Dayal, *The Bodhisattva Doctrine in Buddhist Sanskrit Literature* (London: Kegan Paul, Trench, Trubner and Co., 1932), pp. 209-210.
4. In Theravada, the term Bodhisatta (Pali form of the word) generally refers to Gotama Buddha in a previous life before he became enlightened. In Mahayana Bodhisattvas (Sanskrit form of the term) are special beings who delay their salvation for the sake of helping others, take on the sufferings of others, transfer their merits to them and give them grace: see ACPI [Association of Christian Philosophers of India] *Encyclopedia of Philosophy*, 2010, s.v. "Bodhisattva", by Noel Sheth, S.J., vol. I, pp. 183-187.
5. Khantivadijatakavannana, in Jataka-atthakatha, 4.2.3, No. 313, vol. 72, pp. 34-37. A Sanskrit version is found in the Ksantijataka in the Jatakamala, 28, pp. 189ff. Unless otherwise stated, all references to the Buddhist Sanskrit texts are from the Bauddha-Samskrta-Granthaval edition, published by the Mithila Institute of Post-graduate Studies and Research in Sanskrit Learning, Darbhanga, Bihar.
6. Noel Sheth, "The Buddha's Attitude to Caste", *Negations* 4 (October-December, 1982): 23-26.
7. Assalayanasutta, in Majjhimanikaya, pt II, 43, pp. 403-413; and Vasetthasutta, in Majjhimanikaya, pt II, 48, pp. 462-468.
8. Dhammapada, v. 388, in Khuddakanikaya, pt I, p. 54.

9. Vasalasutta of Suttanipata, 1.7, in Khuddakanikaya, pt I, pp. 287-290.
10. Ambatthasutta, in Dighanikaya, pt I, 3.6, pp. 84-86.
11. On Ksatriya claims to superiority, see G. S. Ghurye, *Caste and Class in India* (Bombay: The Popular Book Depot, 1950), pp. 71-72.
12. Dighanikaya, pt I, 3.6, p. 86.
13. These are monastic lineages or fraternities.
14. Anthony Fernando, "Contemporary Buddhism in Sri Lanka (Ceylon)" in Dumoulin and Maraldo, eds., *Buddhism in the Modern World* (New York: MacMillan and Co., 1976), p. 66.
15. Adele M. Fiske, "Caste among the Buddhists", in Harjinder Singh, ed., *Caste among Non-Hindus in India* (New Delhi: National Publishing House, 1977), pp. 102-103.
16. See his "Caste in India", and "Annihilation of Caste", in Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar, *Writings and Speeches*, vol. 1 (Bombay: The Education Dept., Government of Maharashtra, 1979), pp. 5-96.
17. Gotamisutta, in Anguttaranikaya, pt III, 8.6.1, pp. 370-371.
18. Singalasutta, in Dighanikaya, pt III, 8.5.28 and 30, pp. 146-147.
19. Visuddhimagga, 9.15-38; see Nyanamoli, *The Path of Purification (Visuddhimagga)*, 2nd ed. (Colombo: A. Semage, 1964), pp. 324-332.
20. It is interesting to note the contrary case in the Hindu Bhagavadgita (2.19), where Krishna urges Arjuna to fight against the Kauravas since the soul – which constitutes the essence of a person and is inactive – is neither a slayer nor is slain.
21. See the texts cited in Dayal, *Bodhisattva Doctrine*, pp. 210-212.
22. Kunalajatakavannana, in *Jataka-atthakatha*, 5.21.4, No. 536, vol. 74, pp. 408-410.
23. Tissatheravatthu, in *Dhammapada-atthakatha*, 1.3, pt I, vol.50, pp. 25-29; see Burlingame, *Buddhist Legends*, pt I, pp. 166-170.
24. Unto Tahtinen, *Ahimsa: Nonviolence in Indian Tradition* (London: Rider and Co., 1976), pp. 102-103.
25. *Encyclopedia of Buddhism*, ed. G. P. Malalasekera and others, s.v. "Ahimsa", by Hirakawa, vol. 1, p. 291.
26. *Jatakamala*, 31, vv. 63 and 65, pp. 227-228; 3, p. 16, lines 16-17.

27. Siksasamuccaya, 1.4, p. 16, lines 2-5.
28. Bodhicaryavatara, with the Panjika Commentary, 10, pp. 283-287
29. Jatakamala, 25, v. 29, p. 173.
30. Mahayanasutralankara, 19, v. 28, p. 158; Siksasamuccaya, 7.14, p. 81, lines 16-17. Note that, in addition to this high selfless ideal, some texts do mention other less lofty motives, such as fame, merit, rebirth in a better state, etc.
31. Jataka-atthakatha, 4.2.6, No. 316, vol. 72, pp. 44-47; Jatakamala, 6, pp. 30-35.
32. Jataka-atthakatha, 15.3, No. 499, vol. 73, pp. 359-370; Avadanasataka, 34, pp. 83-85; Jatakamala 2, pp. 7-15.
33. Jataka-atthakatha, 22.10, No. 547, vol. 76, pp. 227-381; Jatakamala, 9, pp. 55-69; Bodhisattvavadanakalpalata, 23, pp. 172-175.
34. Avadanasataka, 55, p. 140.
35. An epithet of any Buddha, but commonly used as an epithet of Gautama Buddha. The word is generally interpreted as “one who has thus (tatha) either gone (gata) or come (agata)”.
36. L’Enseignement de Vimalakirti (Vimalakirtinirdesa), tr. and annotated by Etienne Lamotte, Bibliotheque du Museon, vol. 51 (Louvain: Publications Universitaires, 1962), pp. 216-217.
37. Santideva, Bodhicaryavatara, ed. by Vidhushekhara Bhattacharya, Bibliotheca Indica: A Collection of Oriental Works, Work 280, Issue 1580 (Calcutta: The Asiatic Society, 1960), III, vv. 6-11, 17-18, pp. 31-34.
38. In Theravada (Pali Pacceka-buddha), they attain liberation by their own effort but do not teach others; in Mahayana (Sanskrit Pratyeka-buddha) they do not teach others in the normal way, but do so through thought-transference. However, both in Theravada as well as in Mahayana, they are inferior to Buddhas and, in Mahayana, where the ideal is to become a Bodhisattva, they are also inferior to Bodhisattvas who, unlike Pratyeka-Buddhas, delay their own salvation for the sake of helping others to attain salvation.
39. Siksasamuccaya, 4.7, p. 56.
40. Dighanikaya, pt III, 2.8.27, p. 44.
41. Dhammikasutta, in Anguttaranikaya, pt III, 6.5.16, p.84.
42. Mahaparinibbanasutta, in Dighanikaya pt II, 3.19.62, p. 98.

43. Edward J. Thomas, *The Life of the Buddha as Legend and History* (London: Kegan Paul, Trench, Trubner and Co., 1927), p. 149, n. 3.
44. Amagandhasutta, in *Suttanipata*, 2.2.22-28, pp. 305-306.
45. This does not mean that they were not sensitive to animal life.
46. Jivakasutta, in *Majjhimanikaya*, pt II, 5.1.2, p. 39.
47. Kandarakasutta, in *Majjhimanikaya*, pt II. 1.4.8, p. 8.
48. Brahmanadhammikasutta, in *Suttanipata*, 2.7.88-93, pp. 313-314.
49. Mamsabhaksanaparivartah, in *Saddharmalankavatarasutra*, 8, p. 103, lines 10-11, 24-26; see also vv. 12 and 19, p. 105. The reference to earlier canonical texts that did make exceptions to pure vegetarianism indicates that Buddhism did permit meat-eating in former times.
50. The somewhat defensive attitude of the text in the face of actual criticism against Buddhists consuming meat seems to indicate that the text's pure vegetarianism is proposed as a reaction to this criticism: see Daisetz Teitaro Suzuki, tr., *The Lankavatara Sutra* (London: Routledge and Kegan Paul, 1932; reprinted 1956), p. 211, n. 1.
51. Culahatthipadopamasutta, in *Majjhimanikaya*, pt I, 27.2.8, p. 230.
52. Really speaking, there is no expiation required, but only confession: see I. B. Horner, trans. *The Book of the Discipline*, vol. 2, *Sacred Books of the Buddhists vol.20* (London: Pali Text Society, 1957), p. 3, n. 4.
53. Pacittiya, no.11, pp. 54-56.
54. See Horner, tr., *The Book of the Discipline*, p. 229, n. 4.
55. Pacittiya, no. 10, pp. 52-54.
56. Radhagovinda Basak, ed., *Asokan Inscriptions* (Calcutta: Progressive Publishers, 1959), pp. 71-72.
57. Romila Thapar, cited by Rajmohan Gandhi, *Revenge and Reconciliation: Understanding South Asian History* (New Delhi: Penguin Books, 1999), p. 52.
58. Masaharu Anesaki, *History of Japanese Religion: With Special Reference to the Social and Moral Life of the Nation* (London: Kegan Paul, Trench, 1930; reprint ed., Rutland, Vermont and Tokyo, Japan: Charles E. Tuttle, 1963), pp. 171-172.
59. Basak, *Asokan Inscriptions*, p. 103.

60. Basak, Asokan Inscriptions, p. 4.
61. Encyclopedia of Buddhism, ed. G. P. Malalasekera and others, s.v. "Abhaya-dana," by Shuyu Kanaoka, vol. 1, pp. 20-21.
62. Encyclopedia of Buddhism, ed. Malalasekera, and others, s.v. "Ahimsa", by Akira Hirakawa, vol. 1, pp. 291-292.
63. A.T. Ariyaratne, Collected Works, ed. by Nandasena Ratnapala (vols. 1-3, 6-7), B. A. Tennyson Perera (vol. 4) and Jehan Perera (vol. 5), 2nd ed., 7 vols. (Ratmalana, Sri Lanka: Sarvodaya Vishva Lekha, 1999), vol. 1, p. 43.
64. Ariyaratne, Collected Works, vol. 2, pp. 115-116.
65. Ariyaratne, Collected Works, vol. 4, pp. 43-49.
66. Ariyaratne, Collected Works, vol. 4, pp. 94-100, 103-104.
67. George D. Bond, "A. T. Ariyaratne and the Sarvodaya Shramadana Movement in Sri Lanka", in Engaged Buddhism: Buddhist Liberation Movements in Asia, ed. by Christopher S. Queen and Sallie B. King (Albany: State University of New York Press, 1996), pp. 136-137.
68. Bhikkhu literally means a mendicant and refers to a Buddhist monk: the initial practice of begging for food is now generally defunct, except in a couple of countries like Thailand, Myanmar and Cambodia.
69. H. Uttarananda, "Sihala Buddhist Monks and the Rights of the Tamils", Dialogue n.s. 18:1-3 (January-December 1991): 6-9, 12-13.
70. From the text of the Press Release, sent to me by the Japanese Committee of the World Conference on Religion and Peace.
71. The Island, 5th November 2002, p. 1.
72. Donald K. Swearer, "Sulak Sivaraksa's Buddhist Vision for Renewing Society", in Engaged Buddhism: Buddhist Liberation Movements in Asia, ed. by Christopher S. Queen and Sallie B. King (Albany: State University of New York Press, 1996), pp. 200-208.
73. Sulak Sivaraksa, Loyalty Demands Dissent: Autobiography of an Engaged Buddhist, with a Foreword by the Dalai Lama (Berkeley, California: Parallax Press, 1998), pp. 155-164.
74. "Letter from Cambodia" [a newsletter], March 2002, p. 1.
75. "Editors' Introduction", in Maha Ghosananda, Step by Step: Meditations on Wisdom and Compassion, ed. by Jane Sharada Mahoney

and Philip Edmonds, with a Foreword by Dith Pran and a Preface by Jack Kornfield (Berkeley, California: Parallax Press, 1992), pp. 17-18.

76. The name of the communist group in Cambodia that carried out a massive genocide under the leadership of Pol Pot.
77. Maha Ghosananda, *Step by Step*, pp. 62, 68-69.
78. Aung San Suu Kyi, *Freedom from Fear and Other Writings*, ed. with an Introduction by Michael Aris, with a Foreword to the first ed. by Vaclav Havel and a Foreword to the second ed. by Desmond Tutu, 2nd rev. ed. (London: Penguin Books, 1995), pp. 195-196.
79. Aung San Suu Kyi, *Freedom from Fear*, pp. 360-361.
80. Gandhi, *Revenge and Reconciliation*, p. 400.
81. Dalai Lama, *The Dalai Lama: A Policy of Kindness: An Anthology of Writings by and about the Dalai Lama*, comp. and ed. by Sidney Piburn, with a Foreword by Claiborne Pell, Ithaca (NY: Snow Lion Publications, 1990), pp. 16, 105-106. 133.
82. Dalai Lama, *Freedom in Exile: The Autobiography of the Dalai Lama* (London: Hodder and Stoughton, 1990; New Delhi: Rupa Paperback, 1991; 12th impression, 1994), p. 261.
83. Dalai Lama, H. H. the Dalai Lama: *The Bodhgaya Interviews*, ed. by Jose Ignacio Cabezon (Ithaca, N.Y.: Snow Lion Publications, 1988), p. 32.
84. Dalai Lama, *A Policy of Kindness*, p. 95.
85. Dalai Lama, *Bodhgaya Interviews*, p. 47.
86. Donald Nichols, "A Buddhist Contribution to Peace Spirituality", *Dialogue* n.s. 12:1-3 (January-December 1985): 2-3.
87. Pipob Udomittipong, "Thailand's Ecology Monks", in *Dharma Rain: Sources of Buddhist Environmentalism*, ed. by Stephanie Kaza and Kenneth Kraft (Boston: Shambhala, 2000), pp. 193-194, 196-197.
88. 108 is a sacred number in some Indian religions, including Buddhism.
89. "Bhutan Celebrates Newborn Prince by Planting 108,000 Trees", report filed on 11th March 2016 by Vishal Arora in *The Diplomat* [Asia-Pacific online newspaper]: <http://thediplomat.com/2016/03/bhutan-celebrates-newborn-prince-by-planting-108000-trees/>, accessed on 22nd March 2016.

90. Suttanipata, 1.8, v. 149, in Khuddakanikaya, pt I, pp. 290-291. This simile occurs in Mahayana texts too: e.g., the love (prema) of all beings as if they were one's only child (Saddharmalankavatarasutra, 8, p. 100, line 6).
91. Siksasmuccaya, 12.20, p. 117, lines 9-13.
92. Saddharmapundarikasutra, 5.44, p. 92, line 24.
93. Mahayanasutralankara, 19, v. 5, p. 154.
94. Jatakamala, 8, p. 43, line 1.
95. Siksasamuccaya, 7.14, p. 81, lines 4-5.
96. Mahayanasutralankara, 16, p.103, line 8.
97. Mahayanasutralankara, 3, v. 12; Bodhicaryavatara, with the Panjika Commentary of Prajnakaramati, 8. v. 173, p. 165.
98. A follower of another religion that existed in the Buddha's and Mahavira's time.
99. Tevijjavacchasutta, in Majjhimanikaya, pt II, 21.2, pp. 174-175.
100. Saddharmapundarikasutra, 3.113-135, pp. 66-68.
101. Those who have attained liberation while living.
102. Mahavamsa, 25; see Wilhelm Geiger, tr., The Mahavamsa: The Great Chronicle of Ceylon (London: Pali Text Society, 1912): pp. 177-178, lines 103-111.
103. Nikayasamgraha, cited by Phra Khantipalo, Tolerance: A Study from Buddhist Sources (London: Rider and Co., 1964), p. 105.
104. The History of the Buddha's Religion (Sasanavamsa), tr. by B.C. Law, Sacred Books of the Buddhists, vol. 17 (London: Luzac and Co., Ltd., 1952), pp. 69-79.
105. R. A. Stein, Tibetan Civilization, tr. J. E. Stapleton Driver (Stanford: Stanford University Press, 1972), pp. 69 and 81.
106. The Encyclopedia of Religion, s.v. "Nicherenshu" by Murano Senchu.
107. E. Conze, A Short History of Buddhism (Bombay: Chetana Ltd.), p. 99, cited by Khantipalo, Tolerance, p. 111. See also Ryusaku Tsunoda and others, comps., Sources of Japanese Tradition, 2 vols. (New York: Columbia University Press, 1958; paperback ed. 1964; vol.1 reprinted 1967), vol. I, pp. 217-218.
108. The Encyclopedia of Religion, ed. by Mircea Eliade, s.v. "Mongol Religions", by Walther Heissig, vol. 10, pp. 55-56.

109. What the Buddha Taught, with a Foreword by Paul Demieville, rev. ed. (New York: Grove Press, 1974), p.5.
110. Khantipalo, Tolerance, p. 107.
111. He stayed in a Buddhist monastery for six years, two of which were spent as a monk. Later, however, he joined the Cambodian Communist Party.
112. Robert E. Buswell, The Zen Monastic Experience: Buddhist Practice in Contemporary Korea (Princeton: Princeton University Press, 1992), pp. 24-32.
113. He is referring to the three Semitic or Abrahamic religions, Judaism, Christianity and Islam.
114. Arnold Toynbee, Change and Habit: The Challenge of Our Time (London: Oxford University Press, 1966), p. 167.
115. See the Gospel according to Matthew, 6.12; 18.21-35.
116. Sedakasutta, in Samyuttanikaya, 47.19, pt 5, pp. 144-145.

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